

HARSHA: Intelligent Gesture control Mine Explorer (IGME) Robot

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ABSTRACT

Anti-social activities (terrorism) and natural disasters are very common these days. Locating victims hidden under debris and defusing terrorist activities are time taking processes. In commando operations it is difficult to find the exact location of terrorist and land mines. It is a life risky exercise for commandos to involve in a face to face attack with terrorists. So a robotic system is in need to locate terrorists and intimate the information through video visuals regarding their number and their weapons. This helps in counter acting terrorist attacks in an effective manner. The system can also be used to save civilians covered in debris in no time during earthquakes. The Proposed Intelligent Gesture Control Mine Explorer (IGME) Robot was developed over an Arduino platform. Proposed Intelligent Gesture Control Mine Explorer (IGME) Robot is furnished with temperature, metal and gas detection sensors for gathering the information about its surroundings. This can also be used in various real-time applications like Home security, Mines and Archaeological activities in addition to its usage in defense for terrorist counter attacks and rescue operations.

Keywords: Gesture, Arduino, Terrorist, Archaeology, Night vision, Rescue operation, commando.

INTRODUCTION

Human involvement in mine detection is risky to life. So a human less robot which is equipped with multi sensors, wireless camera is designed. Wireless camera is used to provide live video coverage to control room in order to identify the suspicious regions and which in turn helps in guiding the path for robot. Multi sensors were used to monitor various conditions of surrounding regions like temperature, metals and toxic gases. Sensors were installed which could detect landmines and dangerous gases to protect civilians and soldiers from. Depending upon manual commands the robot can work, manual commands means Gesture signals [1], which can be send through ZigBee [10]. When the robot fails to provide the live video transmission, it need not wait for manual commands from control station. It should capable of taking its own decisions intellectually in the absence of manual commands and can send back data about the status of robot and the environmental conditions. This helps in controlling the movement of the robot easily. So Intelligent Gesture Control Mine Explorer (IGME) Robot is designed to satisfy the above needs. The IGME Robot is named as HARSHA in the name of HARSHAVARDHAN a renowned Indian emperor.

DEMERITS OF EXISTING SYSTEMS

A. Incomplete camera coverage

Unlike man turning his head instead of entire body to watch surroundings the current robots turn their entire structure. Instead of only camera is a major drawback.

B. Fixed robot operation

The existing systems are programmed to search only in a pre-defined path. There is no chance to dynamically alter the search path.

C. Area dependent operation

Area to be covered is predefined and change in shape of search area is not possible.

D. Unintelligent

It works in accordance with the predefined programme. It does not know how to deal an obstacle in that predefined path. In the vicinity of fire, the temperature is too high, at such times the robot cannot move to the safety location.

E. Environmental conditions

It cannot analyse the environmental conditions like temperature, presence of dangerous gases and smoke.

F. Caster wheel based support

Existing robots with three wheels can only move on polished surface but not suitable for rough terrains.

OBJECTIVE

Intelligent Gesture based Mine Explorer (IGME) robot is an innovative robot equipped with Metal, Temperature, IR and gas detection, Video Capturing features useful for landmine detection, locating terrorist in security operations. Locating the

victims and civilians hidden in debris during disaster relief operations.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system has the following specifications:

A. Maximum operating distance is approximately 100mts.

This is the maximum distance from which we can control the robot wirelessly using Control pad. Beyond this the commands may not be received and are responded. There should be a line of sight communication between control pad and controller robot.

B. Two modes of operation.

We can control the robot using wirelessly transmitted commands or self-generated derived by analysing the status from IR sensors. The advantage with this later auto pilot mode is that the robot can take decisions on its own when the camera output is not clear at the remote station.

C. Gesture control.

The major advancement implemented in this system is support for gesture control[1]. The control pad can be attached to either head or hand and a movement can control the robots path.

D. Mine detection.

Designed for detecting the land mines and can be modified even to detect explosive materials.

E. Temperature monitoring.

This helps in remotely monitoring the environmental conditions.

F. Gas leakage monitoring.

Gas leakage monitoring helps us in detecting presence of dangerous gases, which may affect the human life if undetected. This can be further enhanced to find it useful in mining applications.

G. Self-decision ability.

Robot has the capability to take own decisions when no manual commands are available. It can move to a safe location by itself in case of fire accidents.

H. Video streaming.

The robot supports Streaming video to manually analyze the surroundings at the remote station.

I. 360 degrees camera rotation.

Here the camera is not fixed. It was steered to cover complete 360degrees.

BLOCK DIAGRAM OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

Fig1: Block diagram of Transmitter section. Proposed system comprises of two sections

a) Transmitter section and

b) Receiver section

Figure 1 shows the transmitter section. It is composed of the following blocks: ZigBee module, RF camera transmitter, 3-Axis accelerometer [4], Set of push button switches, and Arduino uno[5] which includes Atmega 328 micro controller. Here Arduino [5] is the heart of both transmitter and receiver sections. It was programmed to generate pre-defined commands to rotate motor to choose robot motion according to the applied input signals (tilt in the control pad read using 3-axis accelerometer). ZigBee is used to establish Wireless communication [1] between the Transmitter section and Receiver section. Two sets of push button switch pads are equipped on the control pad. By operating the push button switches we can send the commands to control robot motion manually (even without gesture).

Fig2: Block diagram of Receiver section

Figure2. Details the receiver section. It composes of ZigBee module, motor drivers (L293D)[6], Temperature sensor (LM35)[9], Eddy current loss based Metal detector. Metal Detector cannot interface directly to the arduino, but it is possible with help of opto-coupler (MCT2) [7], Gas sensor (MQ2) [8] and IR sensor, RF camera transmitter section interfaced to Arduino board. For smooth operation of motors, the power output of the controller is not sufficient. So we have used external motor drivers [9] which are powered with 12Volts/1Ah current source. Gas sensor [8] is extremely sensible to CO2 (Carbon dioxide) and CO2 related gases. LM35 is used for temperature measurement. It offers sensitivity about 10mv/1°C. IR sensors not only used for supporting the autonomous mode but also for smoke detection.

MODES OF OPERATION

A. Gesture Mode

Figure 3 explains that the robot will move in accordance to the tilt in control pad [2] [3]. First the Control pad is tilted towards the left side, accordingly robot is moving towards its left. Similarly when control pad is tilted towards the right side, robot is moving towards its right. When the control pad is tilted towards the front side, the robot moves forward. When the control pad is tilted toward the back side, the robot moves backwards.

Fig 3: Gesture based motion of Robot

Table 1 Generation of Gesture signals at transmitter section

S.No	Gesture Control Signals				Command Transmitted
	X-Axis Tilting Angle		Y-Axis Tilting Angle		
	90° Front	90° Back	90° Left	90° Right	
1.	<300	-	-	-	F
2.	-	>385	-	-	B
3.	-	-	<290	-	L
4.	-	-	-	>330	R

Table 2 Gesture Mode Functionality at receiver section

S.No	Received Command	Motor1		Motor2		Motor3		Motor4		Movement Of Robot
		P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	
1.	f	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	Front
2.	r	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	Right
3.	l	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	Left
4.	b	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	Back
5.	s	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Stop

Table 3 Autonomous Mode Functioning Table

S.No	Infrared Input (Autonomous Mode)			Motor1		Motor2		Motor3		Motor4		Movement Of Robot
	IR1	IR2	IR3	P	N	P	N	P	N	P	N	
1.	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	Forward
2.	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	Right
3.	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	Left
4.	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Stop

If the control pad is tilted towards 90° front direction, X-axis will produce the analog signal whose value is < 300 then command 'f' will be transmitted. If the control pad is tilted towards 90° back direction, X-axis will produce the analog signal whose value is > 385 then command 'b' will be transmitted. If the control pad is tilted towards 90° right direction Y-axis will produce the analog signal whose value is < 290 then command 'r' will be transmitted. If the control pad is tilted towards 90° left direction Y-axis will produce the analog signal whose value is > 290 then command 'l' will be transmitted. If the control pad is not tilted and if it is held in parallel to the earth no command will be transmitted, hence robot will not experience any motion.

B. Gesture mode functionality

Table2 shows how gesture mode works. If command 'f' is received then the robot will move forward. If command 'r' is received then the robot will move to right. If command 'l' is received then the robot will move to left. If command 'b' is received then the robot will move backward. If command 'u' is received then the robot will go to User mode. If command 'a' is received then the robot will go to autonomous mode.

C. Autonomous Mode

The operation in autonomous mode is shown in Table 3. Here IR1, IR2 and IR3 sensors are arranged front side, right side, left side respectively to the robot. Three infrared sensors provide data to the micro controller. If all the IR inputs are at low then the robot will move in forward direction. If IR1 is high, the robot will move to its right. If both IR1 and IR2 are high then the robot will move to its left and if all IR's are in high state the robot will stop moving. If no command is given then robot will move backwards.

LIVE VIDEO STREAMING

Receiver is equipped with a RF Camera. Through the visual information provided by the robot, the remote operator at control room can take decisions in form of gestures. Visual information regarding the robot surroundings is provided via the built in transmitter in the camera module. There is no communication between the micro controller and camera module. It works independently as a separate link. RF camera is composed of two parts

- Camera transmitter
- Camera receiver

Communication between camera transmitter and camera receiver happens at 1.2 GHz frequency. Camera module requires the power of 9volts/1Ah. Video encoding and decoding techniques supported by camera module is PAL. Maximum distance covered by the wireless camera is 100Mts. Antenna is connected to the RF camera in the given antenna slot. RF Camera is mounted on robot equipped with necessary steering Mechanism. At the receiving end, tuning is done for satisfactory video clarity.

IGME ROBOT PROTOTYPE

IGMR robot is combination of transmitter section and the receiver section.

Fig 4: Snap shot of Transmitter section (Control pad)

Fig5: Snap shot receiver section (IGME Robot)

SERIAL MONITOR

Here the serial monitor [5] is integrated in the arduino software. Serial monitor [5] is used to monitor data about temperature, presence of landmine, dangerous gas leaks in the robot surroundings. The status of the robot: left, right, forward, backward and stop is also reported on to the serial monitor.

Fig 6: Serial Monitor sample screen shot.

INTERFACING DETAILS

A. Transmitter Section

Table 4 Interfacing at Transmitter section

S.No	Arduino Board Pin Number	Device	
1.	2	ZigBee	Tx
	3		Rx
2.	4	Switch1	
3.	5	Switch2	
4.	6	Switch3	
5.	7	Switch4	
6.	8	Switch5	
7.	9	Switch6	
8.	A0	3-Axis Accelorometer	X-Axis
	A1		Y-Axis
	None		Z-Axis

The above table shows the interfacing details at transmitter section. Here the TX pin of the ZigBee module is connected to the Arduino board pin no2 and similarly Rx pin of the ZigBee [10] module is connected to the Arduino board pin no3. Here the ZigBee module is only used for the serial communication i.e. for sending or receiving the wireless commands to or from the receiver section. A Set of switch pads are interfaced to Arduino board in order to generate the control signals. The switches S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, and S6 are interfaced to Arduino pins as given in Table 4. Switch S1 is used to select the mode of operation, switch S2 to rotate the camera towards left side and

switch S3 is used to rotate the camera towards the right side, and remaining switches S4, S5, and S6 are left for future modifications if any. 3-Axis accelerometer is interfaced to Arduino [5] board in order to generate gesture commands according to the analogue signals provided by 3-Axis accelerometer (ADXL335) [4] when it is tilted.

B. Receiver Section

Tables 5 & 6 gives the interfacing details at the receiver section. The interfacing at receiver side is grouped to two categories based on their power consumption namely high power and low power devices.

i) High Power Devices interfaced at receiver

At the receiver end Motors, ZigBee module [10] and Metal Detectors are considered as the high power Devices which require 12volts/600mA of power. Metal Detector can not interface directly to the arduino, but it is possible with help of opto-coupler (MCT2) [7]. The Motor1 Positive terminal connected to the Arduino board pin no.3 and negative terminal connected to the Arduino board pin no.2. Motor2 positive terminal is connected to the Arduino UNO [5] pin no.5 and negative terminal connected to the Arduino Board pin no. 4. Motor3 positive terminal is connected to the Arduino Board.

Table5 Interfacing high power devices at Receiver section

S.No	Pin Number Of Arduino	Device	
1.	3	Motor1	P
	2		N
2.	5	Motor2	P
	4		N
3.	6	Motor3	P
	7		N
4.	9	Motor4	P
	8		N
5.	10	Camera	P
	11	Motor	N
6.	2	Metal Detector	
7.	0	ZigBee	Tx
	1		Rx

pin no.6 and negative terminal connected to the Arduino board pin no.7. Similarly Motor 4 positive terminal connected to the Arduino board pin no.9 and negative terminal is connected to the Arduino board pin no. 8. Motor which steers the camera is camera motor, its positive terminal is connected to Arduino board pin no.10 and negative terminal is connected to Arduino board pin no.11. TX pin of the ZigBee [10] module is connected to the Arduino board pin no.2 and Rx pin of the ZigBee module [10] is connected to the Arduino board pin no.3. Here the ZigBee module [10] is only used for the serial communication i.e. for receiving the wireless commands which decide the robot motion.

ii) Low Power Devices interfaced at receiver section

At the receiver IR Sensors, Opto-coupler, Temperature Sensor, Gas Sensor and Power Led are considered as the low power devices. They require typically 5Volts /50mA power for their operation. The Power LED is used as the night lamp for supporting the camera during the night times. This is connected to the Arduino board pin no.13. IR Sensors IR1, IR2, IR3 sensors are used in Autonomous mode to take the decisions regarding robot direction of motion in according with data provided by the IR Sensors. IR Sensors IR1, IR2, IR3 are connected to the Arduino board pin no.s 16, 17 and 18 respectively. Temperature Sensor LM35 is connected to analog input pin of the Arduino board pin no.14. Opto-coupler(MCT2) [7] is connected to Arduino board pin no.13. Similarly Gas Sensor is connected to analog input pin of the Arduino board at pin no.15.

Table 6 Interfacing low power devices at receiver section

S.No	Pin Number Of Arduino	Device
1.	13	Power LED
2.	16	IR Sensor1
3.	17	IR Sensor2
4.	18	IR Sensor3
5.	14	Temperature Sensor(LM35)
6.	12	Opto-Coupler(MCT2)
7.	15	Gas Sensor(MQ2)

APPLICATIONS

A. For Landmine detection

In defence this robot can be used for land mine detection

B. In Mining

This robot is used to monitor environmental conditions near mines and alerts the workers during dangerous gas leaks.

C. In Archaeology

During excavations it can even enter in to the places where human cannot enter and reveals the hidden things.

D. In disaster relief and rescue operations

It is difficult and time consuming to find the wound people under the building parts. It can find wound people under the debris very quickly to rescue wound people.

E. In commando and combing operations

In combing or in commando operations it is life risk for the commandos to directly face the terrorists. In such situations these unmanned robots will take the charge and through visual data commandos can locate the terrorists, their number and their weapons. The commandos can take action in accordance. In combing operations the robot will do the same as above and in addition can even locate landmines.

FUTURE SCOPE

IGME Robot is flexible and has main advantage that it can be upgraded. As per our requirements we can extend the robot

features by adding additional sensors. The coverage area can be increased by choosing proper communicating equipment. In next five years, utility for unmanned robots in defence as well as in the commercial sector will grow significantly. A modified IGME Robot will be the reference for the upcoming human less vehicles.

CONCLUSION

The IGME Robot will effectively help in landmine detection and will be useful especially in the commando operations to save the people from anti-social activities and natural disasters. This robot is designed with multiple sensors: temperature, gas leak, and metal, IR sensors for reliable operation in both remote and autonomous modes. As our requirements we can vary the sensitivity of gesture control. For effective utilization, IGME Robot is equipped with battery backup system. We can use this robot for security purpose, with little changes in hardware and in source code.

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